

Physicochemical and Analytical Study of Copper Lactate

O. S. Tomar and P. K. Bhattacharya

The stoichiometry and structure of the copper-lactate chelate has been investigated by the potentiometric and conductometric methods. The compound has been isolated and analysed. The stepwise stability constants of the complex have been determined by Bjerrum's method.

Copper is known to form complexes with a number of ligands¹⁻¹⁰. Lactate complexes of copper have also been studied¹¹. The studies are purely analytical and in alkaline medium. Copper hydroxide gets partially precipitated before the solution is actually alkaline and hence isolation of copper-lactate in alkaline medium would lead to faulty results. The present work is based on physico-chemical studies of the stoichiometry and the stability of copper-lactate and the compound has been isolated in neutral medium.

EXPERIMENTAL AND DISCUSSION

Analar samples of CuSO_4 and lactic acid were used. Solutions were made in conductivity water. Phillips conductivity bridge (Type—PR-9500/80, accuracy 1×10^{-1}), Hungarian pH meter (Type—OP-201/1, accuracy 1×10^{-1}) and Guoy's magnetic balance (Type—Polytronic EMP-75) were used for the study.

The stoichiometry was determined by Job's method of continuous variation (Fig. 1).

FIG. 1.

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The maxima at 06% in the curve corresponds to the dilactate formation. The chelation reaction can be represented as follows:—

Copper ion has been reported to be four coordinate, bonding occurring through dsp^2 hybridization. Since the complex is formed in 1 : 2 ratio, the most probable position of the four coordinating groups will be at the corners of a square plane, the metal atom being connected by two covalencies and two coordinate covalencies. Such a compound should be paramagnetic and the nature has been confirmed by magnetic study.

Isolation of the Compound: The complex was isolated by mixing equimolar solutions of Copper sulphate and lactic acid in the ratio 1 : 2 and precipitating unreacted Copper sulphate, by adding alcohol after few hours. The process was repeated and the filtrate was concentrated on waterbath when a bluish-white solid separated out. It gave the test for lactic acid. The Copper content estimated (26.35%) in this complex corresponded well with the theoretical value (26.91%).

Stability constant: The stability constant of the chelate in solution was found by Bjerrum's method¹², (Fig. 2). $\bar{n}$ values were plotted against pA to obtain the formation curve.

FIG. 2

The values of K_1 , K_2 and K_{AV} work out to be: $K_1=1.585 \times 10^3$, $K_2=8.395 \times 10^2$ and $K_{AV}=1.439 \times 10^3$.

12. J. Bjerrum, G. Schwarzenbach and L. G. Sillen, "Stability constants, part I, Organic ligands", The Chem. Soc., London, 1956.

*Stability constants of Copper Lactate Chelate**Concentrations in mols/lit.*

Dilution	pH	Vol. of 0.02M alkali	Vol. of 0.04M lactic acid	$\bar{n}$	metal- bound ligand $\times 10^4$	free ligand $\times 10^4$	total- ligand $\times 10^4$	(A) $\times 10^4$	1/(A) $\times 10^9$	log 1/(A) or pA
50.40	2.75	0.2ml.	0.1ml.	0.4	0.7936	78.5714	79.365	6.0983	1.6397	3.2146
50.70	2.80	0.4ml.	0.2ml.	0.8	1.5770	77.3170	78.895	6.7917	1.4855	3.1718
52.00	2.85	0.6ml.	0.3ml.	1.2	2.308	74.6100	76.918	7.2900	1.5720	3.1374
58.00	3.25	0.8ml.	0.4ml.	1.6	2.758	66.2100	68.968	16.250	0.6159	2.7891
59.40	3.35	1.0ml.	0.5ml.	2.0	3.367	63.9700	67.337	19.760	0.5106	2.7042
60.00	3.40	1.2ml.	0.6ml.	2.4	3.999	62.6600	66.659	21.720	0.4604	2.6632

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RESEARCH LABORATORIES,
SCHOOL OF STUDIES IN CHEMISTRY,
VIKRAM UNIVERSITY, UJJAIN (M.P.)

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